

Determination of 3-Mercaptopropionic, Mercaptosuccinic and *o*-Mercaptobenzoic Acid by Lead Tetraacetate

KRISHNA K. VERMA & SAMEER BOSE

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur, (M.P.)

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IN an attempt to titrate β -carboxy mercaptans in aqueous solutions by oxidimetric procedures, several anomalies were seen. In each case there was always an excessive consumption to oxidant which varied from one titration of another in an unaccountable fashion. While many water soluble mercaptans are oxidized terminally to disulfides by iodine in aqueous potassium iodide, mercaptans which have a free β -carboxyl group are strongly inclined to further oxidation¹. In a separate procedure involving titration with phenylhydrosulfate, we have observed that the initial concentration of mercaptan is of primary importance in their determination and that there are some mercaptans which are very susceptible to over oxidation.

Three mercaptans mentioned in title, which exhibit a tendency to overoxidation, are estimated based upon the oxidation by excess lead tetraacetate in 60% acetic acid to corresponding sulfonic acids:

Consumptions are high (six equivalents), so that smaller amounts can be determined. The method is simple and suitable for the determination of purity of refined materials. The average error is below 0.5% for 2–50 mg of mercaptan samples.

Reagents

An approximately 0.05M lead tetraacetate solution was prepared by reacting Pb_3O_4 with glacial acetic acid². Its strength was determined iodometrically³. All the three mercaptan samples were gifted from Evans Chemetics, New York, U.S.A., to whom the authors are grateful. Solutions were prepared of 3-mercaptopropionic and mercaptosuccinic acid in distilled water and their strength was determined by titration with mercuric perchlorate⁴. In the case of *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid, the product was recrystallized from benzene to a constant melting point of 164°, and standard solutions were made by dissolving right amounts of it in glacial acetic acid.

Procedure

2–20 ml of sample solution containing 2–50 mg of mercaptan was pipetted into a 250 ml flask. A measured excess (50% suffices) of tetraacetate salt solution was added. Before adding tetraacetate, calculated volume of distilled water (or glacial acetic acid) was added so as to maintain the overall acetic acid concentration very near to 60% by volume.

The flask was left at about 27° for a period of 15 min in the case of 3-mercaptopropionic and mercaptosuccinic acid, and for 30 min when *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid was being determined. Residual lead tetraacetate was estimated by adding a solution of potassium iodide and sodium acetate (100:500 g in 1 l) and titrating the liberated iodine with 0.04N thiosulfate solution to starch end-point. A blank determination was carried in a similar manner to record the hydrolysis of tetraacetate salt.

Results

The recommended procedure appears to be an elegant oxidimetric method for the analysis of three mercaptans mentioned. Reactions are fairly fast in the medium taken; application of lower acetic acid concentration unduly hydrolyzes the tetraacetate salt, although the rate of oxidation increases with decreasing acetic acid concentration. On adding excess of oxidant (as high as four-fold) the results were unaffected. The present method may be applied to other mercaptan samples.

The proposed method has the advantage that the conditions are not critical, and that accurate results are readily achieved even with dilute solutions.

References

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Chemical Study of the Seeds of *Vitex negundo*, L.

G. S. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, A.M. University, Aligarh

&

M. BEHARI

Chemistry Department, S.V. College, Aligarh

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VITEX negundo, L. (Verbenaceae) is an important medicinal plant, and its roots and leaves are used as a tonic and in various ailments¹. The leaves of the drug have been mentioned to contain essential oil², gluconitol, hydroxyaromatic acids and a glucoside³. An alkaloid nishindine⁴, vitamin C, and carotene⁵, and 5-hydroxy, 3,6,7,3',4'-penta-methoxy-flavone⁶ have also been isolated from the leaves. In view of the importance of the drug and since almost no significant work appeared to have been carried out so far on the seeds of the plant, their chemical study was undertaken in these laboratories.